

AGEMERA: FUELLING A GREENER ECONOMY VIA INNOVATIVE MINERAL EXPLORATION

by

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The evolving environmental, economic, and societal requisites within the EU necessitate the development of innovative methods for mineral exploration that align with a transition towards a low-carbon and digital economy. AGEMERA, a three-year Horizon Europe project budgeted at €7.5M (grant agreement N° 101058178), spearheads this initiative by implementing cutting-edge geological and geophysical surveys across approximately 4,700 km², encompassing Finland, Poland, Spain, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Germany, and Zambia (Holma et al. 2022, 2023). AGEMERA aims to map critical raw material (CRM) resources and improve genetic mineral system models for various deposits known to contain CRMs.

Three innovative, non-invasive survey techniques will be showcased during geophysical field trials: passive seismic methods, a multi-sensing drone system integrating magnetic, radiometric, and electromagnetic sensing, and a muographic multidetector density detection system. These novel approaches hold promise for efficient data acquisition and heightened automation, fostering a unique value proposition against traditional geophysical procedures. Still, conventional ground geophysics is also applied.

AGEMERA's geological work encompasses a comprehensive review of selected CRM districts, focusing on their geological, geochemical, and geophysical characteristics and structures involved in mineralisation. The research targets these deposit types: orogenic gold with atypical metal association (e.g., Co), sediment-hosted stratiform copper (e.g., Co), greisen (e.g., Li), karst bauxite (Al), porphyry copper (e.g., PGMs), epithermal gold (e.g., the unknown potential for CRMs), polymetallic veins (e.g., Sb, baryte, Bi, Co, fluorite, W), volcanic-hosted massive sulphide (e.g., Co, In, PGMs), and iron-oxide copper-gold (e.g., Co, REE, P). New geological data are collected by a variety of field research methods. This data, analysed with laboratory studies, yields additional insights into CRMs' distribution, grade, and control. Data also enables computer-based modelling to identify overlooked exploration regions. The final phase enhances or develops new mineral system models for CRM-hosting ore deposits in the selected areas. This information will be vital for present and future project developers to find new ore deposit systems, supporting the sustainability of current mining areas.

AGEMERA assembles twenty partners dedicated to pioneering mineral exploration techniques, fortifying the sustainable supply of CRMs, and advancing the EU's strategic autonomy, thereby fuelling innovation for a greener economy.

REFERENCES

- Holma, M., Korteniemi, J., Casini, G., Saura, E., Šumanovac, F., Kapuralić, J. & Tornos, F. 2022.** Agile Exploration and Geo-modelling for European Critical Raw Materials – Introduction to the AGEMERA project. Institute of Seismology, University of Helsinki, Report S-72, 51–54.
- Holma, M., Peytcheva, I., Šumanovac, F., Tornos, F., Nyambe, I. & Joutsenvaara, J. 2023.** Horizon Europe project AGEMERA: Combining novel methodologies for agile exploration and geomodelling of critical raw materials deposits. Proceedings of the Geological Society of Finland, Vol. 3, Abstracts of the 1st GeoDays 14th–17th March 2023, Helsinki, Finland. University of Helsinki, p. 43.